

PHYLOGENETIC CLASS	ORGANISM	DGAT GENE	SEQUENCE REFERENCE	LITERATURE REFERENCE
eustigmatophyceae (algae)	<i>Nannochloropsis oceanica</i> CMP1779	<i>NoDGAT1</i>	NannoCCMP1779_3520	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT1</i>	NannoCCMP1779_4340	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT2</i>	NannoCCMP1779_3705	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT3</i>	NannoCCMP1779_7206	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT4</i>	NannoCCMP1779_9929	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT5</i>	NannoCCMP1779_3915	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT6</i>	NannoCCMP1779_9590	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT7</i>	NannoCCMP1779_3159	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT8</i>	NannoCCMP1779_358	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT9</i>	NannoCCMP1779_10272	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT10</i>	NannoCCMP1779_5368	[1]
		<i>NoDGTT11</i>	NannoCCMP1779_3592	[1]
<i>NoDGTT12</i>	NannoCCMP1779_3520	[1]		
brassicales (plant)	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	<i>AtDGAT1</i>	NCBI Ref. Seq.: NP_179535.1	[2]
		<i>AtDGAT2</i>	NCBI Ref. Seq.: NP_566952.1	[2]

mammalia (animal)	<i>Mus musculus</i>	<i>MmDGAT1</i>	NCBI Ref. Seq.: NP_034176.1	[2]
	<i>Ratus norvegicus</i>	<i>RnDGAT1</i>	NCBI Ref. Seq.: NP_445889.1	[3]
	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	<i>HsDGAT1</i>	NCBI Ref. Seq.: NP_036211.2	[3]
		<i>HsDGAT2</i>	NCBI Ref. Seq.: NP_835470.1	[3]

Table S5. Information on DGATs sequences used for analysis with PRALINE software.

References:

1. Vieler A, Wu G, Tsai CH, Bullard B, Cornish AJ, Harvey C, Reza IB, Thornburg C, Achawanantakun R, Buehl CJ *et al*: **Genome, functional gene annotation, and nuclear transformation of the heterokont oleaginous alga *Nannochloropsis oceanica* CCMP1779.** *PLoS genetics* 2012, **8**(11):e1003064.
2. Chen JE, Smith AG: **A look at diacylglycerol acyltransferases (DGATs) in algae.** *Journal of biotechnology* 2012, **162**(1):28-39.
3. Cao H: **Structure-Function Analysis of Diacylglycerol Acyltransferase Sequences from 70 Organisms.** *BMC Research Notes* 2011, **4**:249.